

Experimental characterization and modelling of mechanical behavior of microcapsules in composites

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Introduction

Microcapsules are applied in many advanced materials and composites. The concept of the use of microcapsules as sensors of damage indication for high-performance polymer composites is one of the most relevant.

The general aim of the research was to predict mechanical properties of self-sensing polymer composites containing microcapsules. **The specific aim** of the research was experimental characterization and modelling of mechanical properties of microcapsules in composites.

Materials

Melamine-formaldehyde microcapsules with leuco dye (MCD) and with dye activator (MCA), as water based dispersions were supplied by Papierfabrik August Koehler Ag., Germany. The nominal concentration of the microcapsules in the dispersion is $\approx 40\%$ (data from the manufacturer).

Experimental characterization and Modelling of a single microcapsule

Microphoto of damaged microcapsules

The size distribution of MCD obtained by photos treatment.

Nanoindentation curve in the small deformation regime.

Melamine formaldehyde samples quasi-static compression tests.

Geometry of a spherical shell and the displacements u , v , w and internal forces N_α , N_β , and $N_{\alpha\beta}$ operating in the directions of curvilinear axes α , β , and γ .

Testing and modelling: deformed shape of table tennis ball and its FE model.

Force-displacement curves for the empty and filled with the water model system TTB; experiment (solid lines), FEM calculations (dashed lines).

Mechanical behavior of microcapsules in composites

Example of prepared specimens before tensile tests.

Typical stress-strain curves for the polymer films filled with the different concentration of microcapsules.

FE mesh of one eighth of RVE.

Conclusions

Attempt to predict mechanical properties of self-sensing polymer composites containing microcapsules was made. Mechanical properties of single microcapsules and microcapsules in composites were characterized experimentally and modelled. Geometry, size distribution, wall thickness, stiffness and strength of single microcapsules were characterized experimentally. Elastic modulus and compression strength of the shell material were evaluated from experiments and later used for FEM and analytical modelling of microcapsules. Model shells were tested experimentally in compression and successfully modelled that allows to understand mechanical behaviour of single microcapsules and microcapsules in composites. Experimental characterization and modelling of mechanical properties of model composites with microcapsules was performed.

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